

WRITING TECHNIQUE DURING LITERACY TEACHING ON TEACHING

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Abstract: In the article describes the unique features and methods of teaching writing techniques in the alphabet period. When explaining the shape of the letter and its elements, first write it on the board, eliminate mistakes and shortcomings in writing. From the pre-alphabetic era, the stages of learning to write a letter and its elements at the same height, slope and thickness are shown.

Key words: writing, technique, lesson, exercise, fountain pen, letter elements, system, education, hook

Despite the fact that students have completed some exercises during the preparatory period, during the alphabet period, the teacher should recheck the writing instruments while announcing the next lesson. At the same time, it should aim to perform the following tasks:

1. Carrying out gymnastic exercises that increase the movement of finger and hand muscles.
2. Write the exercise on the board and explain what to focus on. (Some students can also dictate how to write the letter)
3. Explain how to use a notebook, where to start writing.
4. To mention the rules of sitting correctly at the desk, holding the pen correctly, holding the notebook correctly.
5. Explaining how many letters to write in each line, regularly monitoring students' writing.
6. After the completion of the first part of the work (depending on the teacher's question), teach them to compare their written work with the sample on the board and find the mistakes they made.
7. Eliminating the shortcomings of students by re-explaining the task.
8. Spend minutes of physical exercise.
9. Explaining the new exercise, determining which page of the textbook, when and how many lines should be written.
10. Teaching to keep the distance between the eyes and the notebook.
11. Analyzing each exercise, giving additional instructions if necessary.

12. Clearly show students the tasks to be performed.

During this period, it is necessary to gradually teach students to use "Husnikhat" notebooks correctly. According to the teacher's instructions, the student should find the necessary exercise in the notebook and perform it. From the pre-alphabetic period, it is necessary to focus on writing the letter and its elements at the same height, slope and thickness.

For copying and writing exercises, not individual letter elements, but separate groups are given.

The implementation of these requirements in the pre-alphabetic period creates an opportunity to conduct the lesson more effectively in the alphabetic period.

During the alphabet period, students are introduced to speech sounds, learn to form words, read words and sentences, and write words and sentences with the participation of some elements, letters, and crossed letters. Teaching children to write is very important during the alphabet period. During this period, students are taught the letter and its elements in the order shown in the "Alphabet" notebook. Students should be reminded of the rules of writing hygiene from time to time.

The main graphic works performed during the alphabet period are:

1. Write lowercase and uppercase letters in alphabetical order.
2. Adding letters in syllables and words.
3. Teaching to write without interrupting hand movements.
4. To teach to keep the slant and width of the letters correctly.

When writing the shape of the letters by the students, it is necessary to review their writing, to show the correct spelling of the element to the students who write the element of some letters incorrectly. During this period, students make mistakes such as not writing letters completely, and writing letters interchangeably. In the alphabet period (and in the second half of the academic year), the texts written by students can be analyzed in three different ways:

- a) determine the composition of the word;
- b) determine the meaning of the word;
- c) work on the graphic representation of exercises.

Taking all of this into account, the placement of the exercises in the "Husnikhat" notebook is given on the basis of the "Alifbe" book.

During the alphabet period, students should be taught to write syllables, and later to write words as a whole.

Some students try to write words by letters separately, this should not be allowed at all, because as a result of writing letters separately, some letters are left out and replaced. During this period, students should be taught to write by heart. For this, it is necessary to give the following tasks: read the text, look at how it is written, write without looking at the board, read, compare with the example.

At the end of the alphabet period, writing skills are formed in most students, but without being satisfied with this, it is necessary to improve the skills of teaching writing. Below we will show how to teach the lowercase letter "r".

Lesson topic. Teaching to write the lowercase letter "r" correctly and beautifully.

The progress of the lesson.

Students, what sound did we learn from the book "Alifbe" in the previous lesson? Name the words that have this sound in the middle, at the end, and at the beginning of the word (students will find the word). Now find the lowercase r from the cursive alphabet. Here is a print of the lowercase r. Now we will learn how to write a letter with you. (The teacher shows on the board.) From which side I am writing and in which direction I am pointing my hand: look at it.

The lowercase letter r is made up of two elements, the first element consists of two overlapping wavy elements, and the second element is in the form of a small stick with a hook underneath. But when writing, we write by adding both elements to each other, the hand movement is not interrupted when writing this letter.

-Look, how I write the first element of the letter, starting from 1.5 mm below the middle line of the notebook, we write it in a slanted and looped form, and we write the second element in the form of a straight linear loop from the top line down.

When writing this letter, pay special attention to its slant. Let it be parallel to the slope of the notebook.

When running the pen back over the line, don't make it too thick, as the letter should be the same thickness.

- Come on, readers, before you start writing this letter, tell me how to sit at the desk while writing? Where should our feet stand? How do we handle the gavda? (Students answer.) With which fingers do we hold the pen? Where is our index finger? Let's check how we handle the car. When we say "one" we raise

our index finger, when we say "two" we lower it. (Students raise their pen and show their index fingers).

Now let's check if our notebook is correct. We adjust the outer edges of the notebook to the slanted line on the desk. Let's start writing the letter. You also write the letters evenly as I have shown in your notebook. Do not write more than 10 in a row.

After that, the teacher checks the students' notes and gives appropriate instructions if necessary, and the students practice by writing two more lines.

After students acquire the skill of writing the lowercase r, words are written from the "Husnikhat" notebook: bee, saw, pomegranate, ball.

Before writing the words to the students, the teacher shows their connection on the board and reminds that the small letter r is written by joining the letters before and after it without interrupting the hand movement.

After writing a line, short verbal instructions are given so that the students' hands are not tired.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher mentions some typical mistakes of the students and the students who wrote the best, gives a homework: to write two lines of the lowercase letter r and the words with this letter.

In the first grade, in the second half of the academic year, in mother tongue lessons, one should pay attention to the orthographic aspect of writing and not forget about its graphic aspect. Writing some letters can be practiced not for one or two days, but for several days. But the type of exercises should be different. The materials given in the book "Husnikhat" for the second half of the year are not divided into hours or parts like in the alphabet period. The teacher can choose writing exercises according to the subject of the mother tongue.

Homework is assigned to find and write words that contain this letter. If the students still do not master the writing of this letter well, it can be repeated in the next lessons. Sometimes words made from this letter can be copied and written from the "Husnikhat" notebook.

Capital letters, like lowercase letters, are divided into groups. For example, letters L and M with similar elements can be practiced in one lesson. When practicing capital letters, students can write the names of cities and rivers, and the names of people.

Below, we will show you how to conduct husnikhat exercises as a part of the native language lesson.

Lesson topic: pronunciation and writing of consonants d and t.

The progress of the lesson.

At the beginning of the lesson, the following questions and answers will be held with the students.

1. What is the sentence made of?
2. What is a word made of?
3. What do we do with sound?
4. What are sounds represented in writing?

After that, the new topic will be presented.

Before explaining the pronunciation and writing of the consonants d and t to the students, the new topic is practiced by writing the letters d and t in two lines in the "Husnikhat" notebook based on the rules of beautiful writing. Before starting to write the letters, it is mentioned again about how they are written, what elements they are made of, and how they are connected with other letters: the lowercase letter t is made up of two elements, which are written with the hand separated. With other letters, it is written together, regardless of where the word appears. The lower case d is explained in the same way. Then the material related to this topic from the "Mother Tongue" textbook will be explained and exercises will be performed. After teaching the exercise to 3-4 students, the words with the consonants d and t are written down. After that, you can write proverbs and riddles suitable for the new topic.

Such connection of husnikhat exercises with native language lesson is the basis for formation of correct and beautiful writing skills and thorough mastery of native language science.

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